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Research Article

**A SURVEY TO ASSESS THE IMPACT OF PRINT &
ELECTRONIC MEDIA ON POLIO ERADICATION AMONG
PROVINCES OF PAKISTAN INCLUDING URBAN & RURAL
AREAS**¹Dr. Anas Ahmad Shah, ²Dr. Fawad Munawar, ³Dr. Taabeer Malik¹DHQ Hospital Faisalabad²Punjab Medical College Faisalabad³Services Hospital Lahore**Abstract:**

Objectives: The Key goal of the research survey was to discover the role of electric media (television, radio, newspaper) on established polio inoculation dosages in homes in altogether districts of Pakistan. The purpose was to associate polio inoculation in homes who had contact with electric media (television, radio, newspaper), through families who had no contact with electric media.

Methodology: Pakistan Demographic and Health Survey (PDHS) 2014-15, 4th nationwide review, facts were practised for this survey. In this study, 15,010 households remained nominated (6,950 in city parts and 7,060 in urban/rustic parts) and here remained 12,945 engaged homes. From those engaged homes, 13,560 ever-married female and 3,136 forever wedded male age 17-47 were interrogated. SPSS Multinomial Logistic Reversion investigates was practised to get the numerical meaning and to examine suggestion among electric media and polio inoculation doses. A p-value of <0.06 was measured to remain statistically important.

Results: TV was additional actual as compared to radio in polio inoculation. Offspring from homes who got television and radio established extra polio inoculation doses as compared to offspring from homes who got no television plus radio. Homes who had the facility of TV had meaningfully developed polio inoculated offspring, inoculation times on cards and inoculation described through moms as compared to these homes who had no facility of television. Rustic parts of Pakistan, deprived of radio and television in homes, got added polio unvaccinated offspring as compared to city parts. In Baluchistan rustic zones, homes having no radio got 38.8% to 75.2% plus homes having no tv got 38.4 % to 81.6% polio unvaccinated offspring which is very poor proportion in Pakistan. Radio and tv remained statistically important and had a connotation having polio inoculation quantities.

Conclusion: Electric media, tv, and radio, got a significant part in polio inoculation and may perform a vigorous part in polio abolition in our country. Appropriate scheming and distribution of influential media posts at appropriate period might make alertness about polio, variation behaviour and arrogance for polio inoculation.

Keywords: Poliomyelitis, Electric Media, Pakistan, Inoculation

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INTRODUCTION:

Poliomyelitis is a very pathological illness which largely disturbs offspring below 4-5 years. Poliovirus is mostly spread over faecal-verbal way and verbal emissions. The worm attacks mental arrangement and may produce paralysis. Inappropriately, there is no cure for Poliomyelitis and this may solitary remain prohibited by inoculation and vaccination [1]. Lacking vaccination, protected structure receipts additional than a week to know how to contest off mysterious creatures and that period is sufficient for mounting/dispersion microorganisms to grow illness [2]. In June 1973 EPI was on track through World Health Assembly to exclude offspring internationally and in 1989, it approved determination for the universal abolition of Poliomyelitis [3]. In our country, EPI was initiated in 1977 through the aim of the abolition of Poliomyelitis by the year 2011 [4]. Through 2015, a whole of 7,850 Severe flabby paralysis situations remained described in the country, in Punjab area, 3942 stood with most described situations [5]. This is assessed that around 300,010 offspring of fewer than 4-5 years of age are existing in Poliomyelitis widespread parts in our country. While, in the country here is weakening in Poliomyelitis situations, but then those are never episodic [6]. In our country, deprived information around inoculation/immunization plus bad thinking sideways through spiritual issue cut Poliomyelitis immunization [7]. The recurrence of Poliomyelitis situations within our country expresses the danger to societies at local and worldwide side by side [8]. DG of WHO has cautioned global feast of desolate polio warm and declared it PHEIC [9].

Electronic media may revolute the thinking, generate consciousness, diminish anxiety plus inspire individuals for polio inoculation [10]. Electric media (radio, television) may teach people, also being an influential instrument, it must be practised to sight anticipated societies. Electric media (radio, television) may have an influence on Poliomyelitis immunization [11]. A key goal of the research survey was to discover part of electric media on established Poliomyelitis inoculation dosages in families in all areas of Pakistan. The purpose stood to associate Poliomyelitis immunization in families that got contact with electric media, television and radio,

through families who got no contact to electric media, radio and television.

METHODOLOGY:

PDHS 2014-15 was the 4th study led in our country as part of worldwide Demographic plus DHS database. The study was led in all areas of our country without AJK, FATA, and limited armed also endangered parts. The arena work of study was completed at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore from September 2017 to October 2018. Methodical specimen method was practical and 14,010 homes, 6,950 in city zones and 7,060 in country areas, were nominated. From 13,466 engaged homes, 12,946 families were questioned. From nominated families, 13,560 ever-wedded females and 3,136 forever wedded males age 17-47 remained questioned. The answer proportions of females were 96% and 78% of males. Numerical Bundle for SPSS was done for irritated tabularization to express benches to measure part of electric media with established polio injection dosages in altogether districts of Pakistan. The connection among radio and tv (sovereign variables) and Poliomyelitis injection dosages (reliant on variables) were verified by SPSS Multinomial Logistic Regression examines. A p-value of <0.06 was measured to be statistically important.

RESULTS:**Radio contact in families and Poliomyelitis immunization**

Table 1 displays established Poliomyelitis injection dosages in families who got no radio, whereas table 2 displays established Poliomyelitis injection dosages in families that got radio contact. Tables 1 and 2 prove that offspring established extra Poliomyelitis inoculation dosages, in families who got radio experience as compared to offspring who got no radio experience in families. Offspring from families who got radio established developed Poliomyelitis injection dosages plus immunization described by moms as compared to offspring from families who got no radio. In dissimilarity, immunization days on cards of established Poliomyelitis inoculation dosages remained extra in families who got no radio as compared to families who got a radio. In the rustic zone of Baluchistan, 77.4 % offspring in families lacking radio did not obtain Poliomyelitis 0 dosage, and this was the hugest proportion found in Pakistan.

Table – I: Families who got no radio and Poliomyelitis immunization

Areas and Replies (8662)		Islamabad	Punjab		Sind		Khyber Pakhtunkhwa		Baluchistan		Gilgit Baltistan
		Urban	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban
Polio 1	No	12.6	6	6	13.8	21.9	14.5	27.6	22.9	38.8	18.7
	Timely immunization	36.1	39	29	32.2	6.9	32.5	26.8	10	3.8	17.2
	Mom described, Yes	52.7	55.9	66.1	56	74.4	56.3	48.8	67.2	65.7	18
Polio 2	No	20.4	11.6	10.8	22	6.9	18.9	33.2	26	60.2	25
	Timely immunization	35.7	36.6	26.7	28.6	5.3	29.8	24.4	9.8	39.5	15.8
	Mom described, Yes	46.2	54.6	65.5	51.5	69.3	55.6	45.2	64.2	35.7	32.6
Polio 3	No	29.7	16.3	15.2	30.8	34.4	23.7	37.8	23	9.6	4.8
	Timely immunization	32.6	33.6	23.9	24.9	4.4	26.2	21.2	9.3	23.6	31.7
	Mom described, Yes	42.6	52	63.9	46	64.3	53.4	43.7	13.7	42.8	23.9
Polio 0	No	18.5	21.8	36	22.8	45	22.4	40.2	63.9	9.4	13.1
	Timely immunization	39.1	39.2	27.3	33.4	8.3	33.8	26.9	25	47.8	9.3
	Mom described, Yes	44.8	41.3	36	46.3	48	42.8	35.8	64.3	34	24.3

Table – II: Families taking radio and polio immunization

Areas and Answers (1860)		Islamabad	Punjab		Sind		Khyber Pakhtunkhwa		Baluchistan		Gilgit Baltistan
		Urban	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban
Polio 1	No	6	1	6	13.8	17.4	14.5	29.3	22	7	20.6
	Timely immunization	38.6	21.7	42.1	51.3	9	31.4	42.5	26.9	2.6	7.8
	Mom described, Yes	24.6	36.5	31.2	61.1	73.5	16.9	10.4	67.2	65.7	18.6
Polio 2	No	19.5	14.3	21	24.1	7	52.3	36.3	26	60.2	20
	Timely immunization	21.7	36.6	15.7	28.6	15.5	16.4	51.3	21.4	29	13.3
	Mom described, Yes	37.2	54.6	65.5	28.5	31.6	17.4	15.8	27.4	27.6	12.9
Polio 3	No	7.7	16.3	15.2	17.8	19.3	16.3	9	26.3	17.3	24.6
	Timely immunization	9.6	33.6	23.9	41.9	28.6	17.3	49	3.4	23	9.1
	Mom described, Yes	21.6	23	36.9	21.4	9.2	25.5	18.4	34.6	9.1	31.6
Polio 0	No	18.5	21.8	36	16.8	7.1	28.5	45.9	51	19.3	32.5
	Timely immunization	39.1	39.2	27.3	31.4	17.4	31.5	16	48.3	32.5	19.5
	Mom described, Yes	44.8	41.3	36	46.3	21.2	21.5	37.4	63.6	9.1	17.4

TV experience in families and their effect on established polio injection dosages. Table III displays polio injection dosages established in families who got no TV and table IV shows polio inoculation dosages established in families who got access to a TV. Those tables disclose that offspring from families with TV access had established noticeably extra polio injection dosages, advanced immunization days on card and inoculation described meaningfully extra by moms as compared to offspring as of families who got no access to a TV. In the rustic zone of Baluchistan, 81.7% broods in families without television did not obtain polio 0 dosage and it displayed uppermost numeral in Pakistan.

Table – III: Families who got no television access and polio inoculation

Areas and Answers (4296)		Islamabad	Punjab		Sind		Khyber Pakhtunkhwa		Baluchistan		Gilgit Baltistan
		Urban	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban
Polio 1	No	7.1	26.9	21.2	29.9	17.9	24.6	38.5	10.1	17.8	19.6
	Timely immunization	19.4	18.6	23.3	31.8	19.3	15.3	8.9	17.7	2.8	17.8
	Mom described, Yes	28.9	46.5	11.2	41.1	73.5	16.9	10.4	27.2	35	18.6
Polio 2	No	9.6	14.3	31	21.1	7	22.3	36.3	26	30.1	20
	Timely immunization	25.6	36.6	25.7	18.6	15.5	16.4	31.3	21.4	29	13.3
	Mom described, Yes	31.1	14.6	35.5	28.5	31.6	17.4	15.8	27.2	28.6	12.9
Polio 3	No	26.9	37.6	19.4	26.6	27.4	25.7	17.6	36.4	18.4	24.6
	Timely immunization	16.3	24.5	28.5	32.4	19.9	26.9	16.1	13.8	14.2	37.1
	Mom described, Yes	18.3	42.9	30	12	18.5	13.4	17.3	34.9	24.1	24.2
Polio 0	No	15.6	15.7	27.5	25.5	16.3	15.3	26.6	21.1	17.3	42.5
	Timely immunization	22.4	16.9	18.5	22.9	24.5	22.6	26.7	28.3	22.5	39.1
	Mom described, Yes	32.5	27.6	27.3	37.8	16.9	16.6	17.2	13.6	29.1	37.3

Table – IV: Families who got no television access and polio inoculation

Areas and Reply (6230)		Islamabad	Punjab		Sind		Khyber Pakhtunkhwa		Baluchistan		Gilgit Baltistan
		Urban	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban
Polio 1	No	15.1	18.7	25.2	18.3	14.7	15.6	17.5	25.3	27	29.7
	Timely immunization	27.7	13.2	24.3	18.3	27.6	18.5	21.6	31.7	31.1	49.8
	Mom described, Yes	13.7	23.4	32	41.7	38.8	21.8	29.6	36.4	34.6	15.2
Polio 2	No	26.6	26.6	33.6	29.6	18.4	31.4	24.8	41.5	37.2	17.4
	Timely immunization	21.7	36.6	15.7	28.6	15.5	16.4	51.3	21.4	29	13.3
	Mom described, Yes	9.6	32.5	38.4	28.5	31.6	17.4	15.8	31.3	15.4	12.9
Polio 3	No	37.8	17.2	25.2	17.8	19.3	16.3	14.3	23.4	17.5	31.6
	Timely immunization	39.2	21.5	25.6	41.9	41.3	17.3	31.4	3.4	13.3	19.1
	Mom described, Yes	29.3	27.3	36.9	21.4	39.2	25.5	18.4	34.6	29.1	29.6
Polio 0	No	48.4	24.6	36	16.8	24.3	28.5	14.9	51	14.3	21.5
	Timely immunization	31.7	29.3	27.3	31.4	27.4	31.5	36.4	48.3	31.5	19.5
	Mom described, Yes	14.3	23.8	36	46.3	23.2	24.5	46.1	63.6	26.3	17.4

Figure 1 and 2 display arithmetical implication and connection of radio and television with polio inoculation dosages. The charts evidently demonstrate that there is arithmetical consequence and association of radio and TV with polio inoculation dosages (1,2,3,0). SPSS Multinomial Logistic Deterioration model was practised for studies.

Figure – I: Families having radio connotation with polio inoculation dosages

P-Value	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
Chi-Square	49.978	51.783	38.335	48.437

Figure – II: Families having television and connotation of polio inoculation dosages

P-Value	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
Chi-square	600.487	391.228	314.794	281.773

DISCUSSION:

This research displays that electric media (radio and Television) experience in families has a huge influence on polio inoculation. It displays that offspring established extra polio inoculation dosages in families who had radio and TV. Offspring in families who got TV had decidedly tall polio inoculation dosages, inoculation noticeable on card and inoculation described by mom in contrast to offspring from families who got no Television. Radio and Television have statistical meaning and connection with polio injection dosages. Present interim outcomes of 5th inhabitants and housing survey 2017 display that our country's populace is 207, 780, 523 and yearly progress amount (1999 to 2017) are 22%. Rendering to the World Bank estimate, its populace will be 234,378,000 in 2028 and 33% inhabitants will be underneath 13 years of age. Residents under 4-5 years of age in our country desire distinct care and actions for polio immunization. PDHS 2014-15 supposed that there is a huge sum of offspring in our country that did not get polio inoculation and they may get polio disease. Deprived information around polio immunization and diverse fences have placed kids' health at Palisade and here is a necessity to spread each misused kid for polio immunization concluded tall superiority vaccination actions. This is likely by nationwide movements by usage of electric media (radio and Television) to except offspring from polio disease. Electric media (radio & Television) may meaningfully progress polio immunization attention in Pakistan. It requires huge excellence radio and Television ads at an appropriate period for generating consciousness around polio, educating information about illness belongings, lessening terror and humanizing societies for polio inoculation. While example magnitude of PDHS 2014-15 was minor but it provided compulsory info of electric media effect on polio immunization.

CONCLUSION:

Electric media, Television and radio, got a significant part in polio immunization and may act a significant part in polio abolition in our country. Appropriate scheming and distribution of commanding media posts at appropriate period may generate consciousness regarding polio, variation behaviour and attitude for polio immunization.

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